

HIGH-STRENGTH, HIGH-DISSIPATION CARBON NANOTUBE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The interfacial sliding motion of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) within a polymeric hosting matrix gives rise to energy dissipation. By tuning the interfacial shear strength (ISS) of the CNT-matrix interface, the dissipation can take place within tunable ranges of strain amplitudes. This is the basis for conceiving new multilayered carbon nanotube nanocomposites in which different layers with tunable ISS can lead to a concurrent optimization of strength and dissipation, often seen as two conflicting targets. Such optimization is tackled by a novel meso-mechanical nonlinear inelastic model proven to effectively predict the damping capacity of CNT nanocomposites. The proposed elastoplastic, rate-independent, constitutive theory is based on the mean-field homogenization method which combines the Eshelby equivalent inclusion method, the Mori-Tanaka homogenization, and the concept of inhomogeneous inclusions with inelastic eigenstrains introduced to describe the inelastic stick-slip. Since the ISS parameter plays a key role in the nanocomposite strength and dissipation, the current work seeks to improve the strength and damping properties by suitable interfacial CNT-matrix functionalization. Variations of the ISS parameter can be achieved by a functionalization that affects the chemical bonds between CNTs and hosting matrix. A set of experimental tests - including DMA analysis, calorimetry and spectroscopy – aims to evaluate the influence of the ISS parameter, together with other constitutive parameters, on the nanocomposite strength and damping capacity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotube nanocomposites are believed to have the potential to exhibit high damping capacity and excellent mechanical properties. The superior Young modulus of the carbon nanotube fillers enables a structural reinforcement when the load transfer is ensured by a strong interaction between the CNTs and the surrounding polymer matrix. On the other hand, high dissipation can be observed when a frictional sliding motion takes place through the high interfacial area, available between the CNTs and the polymer chains. This dissipative phenomenon at the CNT-matrix interface, known as stick-slip mechanism, has been extensively studied [1]. The great potential of the CNT composites lies in the possibility to tailor the CNT/matrix interface, allowing for the design of a new class of lightweight materials with desired properties. Several studies highlighted the importance of various factors that can affect the behavior of such nanostructured materials, including the CNT dispersion,

their aspect ratio and alignment [2, 3], as well as the mechanical/thermal properties of the polymer matrix.

Short CNTs can facilitate the occurrence of the stick-slip phenomenon as well as the disentanglement during the fabrication process. At the same time, the orientation of the CNTs can improve the response of the material designed to work under specific loading conditions. On the other hand, the ability of the polymer chains to react with some functional groups or to interact with the aromatic rings of the CNTs surface is the key for tuning the interfacial properties. It can be safely stated that, together with the CNT weight fraction, the interfacial shear strength is the main factor affecting the nanocomposite response [4]. By acting at the nano-scale level and performing a proper chemical and/or physical functionalization of the CNT outer walls, it is possible to modify the ISS and optimize the macroscopic response of the material.

To optimize the complex behavior of the CNT-nanocomposite material, a novel meso-mechanical, nonlinear constitutive model has been developed to effectively predict the mechanical and dynamic response of nanocomposites [5]. Micro- and macro- constitutive parameters of the nanocomposites, such as the ISS, the CNT volume fraction and orientation within a multilayered composite, can be optimized to obtain a material with specific damping capacity and mechanical strength. Only a few works have dealt with experimental data on the mechanical and hysteretic damping behavior of nanocomposites [6]. The present work addresses identification of the material model parameters through experimental tests and the actual feasibility of tuning these parameters through a carefully designed manufacturing/fabrication process of the nanocomposite material. Thus, a preliminary study on the influence of several key factors is carried out and a detailed study into the processing and manufacturing techniques and their influence on such key factors is provided.

2 MODELING OF THE CNT COMPOSITE MECHANICAL RESPONSE

The nonlinear constitutive model adopted for the prediction of the CNT composite behavior [5] shows the key role of the CNT volume fraction and the interfacial shear strength. The employed mean-field homogenization method is based on application of the Eshelby equivalent inclusion method and the Mori-Tanaka average stress/strain theorem. On the other hand, the introduction of an inelastic eigenstrain field in the CNT inclusions accounts for the occurrence of the interfacial stick-slip between the CNTs and the surrounding matrix. Indeed, this inelastic eigenstrain has the aim to reproduce the local slip behavior occurring at the CNT-matrix interface. The effective stress driving the evolution of this inelastic component is the von Mises function of the interfacial stress jump.

The influence of the ISS parameter (Fig. 1) is such that for relatively high ISS, the curve representing the nanocomposite damping flattens out over a wide strain bandwidth. A differential evolutionary-based optimization of the material parameters of the nanocomposite was carried out with respect to the CNT volume fraction and the ISS.

Fig. 1: ISS sensitivity in CNT/epoxy composites: damping ratio vs. strain amplitude.

The numerical results provided by the adopted nonlinear constitutive model have shown a good match with other complex molecular dynamic and micromechanical models [7]. Such a unique nonlinear meso-scale model needs a calibration of the material parameters based on sets of experimental measurements.

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK: FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CNT NANOCOMPOSITES

The validation of the theoretical model requires a campaign of mechanical tests carried out using the Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer TA Q800. Since the CNT/polymer composites are mostly conceived for structural applications, the chosen high-performance polymer matrices hosting the CNTs are either thermosetting or thermoplastic. As thermosetting polymer, the epoxy resin Harz L20, together with the hardener EPH161, is chosen because of its high static/dynamic strength (Young modulus of 3.4 GPa) and its low viscosity, which facilitates the integration of nanofillers. Moreover, to compare the interfacial interactions, a high-performance thermoplastic polymer, Polyamide-6 (Ultrad B27 E) is chosen since it is tough and exhibits high heat and solvent resistance, with melting point at 220°C.

The sample preparation involves several techniques, such as the in-situ polymerization method, for the preparation of nanocomposite samples with the epoxy, and the use of the melt mixing method for the preparation of the thermoplastic nanocomposites with Polyamide-6. Low weight fractions of multi-walled CNTs (MWNT) Nanocyl NC7000 were employed in the samples preparation. NC 7000 MWNTs are characterized by a length of 1.5 μm and an average diameter of 9.5 nm (carbon purity 90%). This low aspect ratio prevents the formation of CNT agglomerations, enhancing the dispersibility of the nanotubes in the matrix. Moreover, the short length of the nanotubes may accelerate the stick-slip occurrence. The geometry and dimensions of the specimens were chosen in agreement with the requirements for the three-point bending and single cantilever mechanical tests using DMA Q800. Neat polymer samples and CNT-polymer composite samples were manufactured and compared (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Neat epoxy samples and CNT/epoxy composite samples with 0.5wt% of CNTs for three-point bending and single cantilever mode tests with DMA.

The in-situ polymerization technique for the CNT/epoxy composites is a multi-step process that requires a first dispersion of the CNTs in the resin L20 by using a Speed Mixer DAC 400 FV, at 1800 rpm for 5 min, followed by an ultrasonic bath for 1.5 h at controlled temperature (30°C). The mixture is then degassed in a vacuum oven for 1 h. Finally, the hardener EPH161 is added into the mixture at resin-to-hardener weight ratio equal to 4:1. The filling of the metal mold takes place at 40°C under a controlled vacuum system in order to avoid bubbles formation in the sample. The curing and post curing process is carried out at room temperature for 24 h and at 60°C for 10 h. The melt mixing technique for the CNT/PA-6 composite represents, instead, a more appealing process for potential industrial application due to the easier processing of the thermoplastics. The weighted amounts of PA-6 and MWNTs were introduced and mixed in a DSM Explore twin screw microcompounder, at 240°C with rotational speed of the screws at 150 rpm for 5 min. The high shear force at very high temperature provided by the device allows good dispersion of the MWNTs in the polymer matrix. The material is subsequently compression molded at 250°C with a pressing force of 50 KN for 2 min.

The morphology and degree of dispersion in the nanocomposite samples was investigated using a light microscopy. A good degree of CNT dispersion was achieved in the thermoplastic nanocomposite, with an optimization of the parameters during the melt mixing process (rotational speed, temperature and time of the mixing). Fine-tuning of the process was required to achieve a good dispersion of MWNTs in the epoxy nanocomposite. Indeed, CNTs generally tend to agglomerate in epoxy polymers due to the insolubility of the CNTs in these molecular structures. In this case, CNT functionalization turns out to be, not only an answer for the ISS tuning in nanocomposites, but also an efficient technique for minimizing the CNT agglomeration in polymer matrices. The chemical (covalent) functionalization can take place by adding various functional groups on the CNTs surface. The best functional-group candidates for this functionalization are the carboxyl groups (-COOH) and the amino groups (-NHR). The choice between those two molecules is led by the quality and efficiency of the final interactions between the CNTs and the polymer chains. Nevertheless, both functionalization processes, namely with the carboxylic groups and the amino groups, are taken into account.

The carboxyl-functionalization is pursued with the main objective of improving the CNTs dispersion in the hosting matrix, by preventing CNT agglomerations. Instead, amino-functionalization, in the specific case, can be advantageous thanks to their high reactivity with the selected polymers.

A first series of mechanical tests was carried out with the epoxy nanocomposite samples. Three-point bending tests and single cantilever tests were performed and yielded the (flexural) storage and loss modulus of the nanocomposites. Moreover, variation of the loss factor with temperature and frequency will be investigated in the near future. The tests were mostly used for the identification of the model parameters, such as the ISS, and provided the first evidence of the sought optimal damping behavior.

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